

Accuracy of Star Mapper Observations

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1. Notations:

Baseline values:

B	-	blue magnitude of star	-
s	-	star mapper grid period (in the scanning direction)	3.0
δ	-	star mapper ratio (clear band)/(grid period)	0.2
$N_1; N_2$	-	number of slits (1: vertical, 2: inclined 45°)	8; 8
Δt	-	sampling period	1/1200 sec
v	-	spin rate = scan speed	150 "/sec
$I(t)$	-	modulated intensity behind grid (expected count rate)	-
b	-	sky background + dark current (count rate)	-
λ_{eff}	-	effective wavelength	0.45 μm
D	-	length (diameter) of entrance pupil	25 cm
MTF(ξ)	-	normalized modulus of optical transfer function	
ξ	-	normalized spatial frequency, $\xi = \lambda_{\text{eff}}/sD$ for first harmonic	
A	-	entrance pupil area for each FOV	200 cm^2
η, ζ	-	coordinates in slit system, η along scan, ζ perpendicular to scan	

2. Modulated intensity

(2)

The expected photomultiplier count rate (in counts per sec or Hz) is the sum of the background (sky + dark) current b and the modulated star light. The latter contains a finite number (n) of harmonic components, viz.

$$n = \text{entier} [sD/\lambda_{\text{eff}}] \quad (1)$$

or $n=8$ with the values given in section 1. The expected count rate will then be (neglecting the finite extent of the grid):

$$I(t) = b + I_0 \left\{ 1 + \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \cos(k 2\pi vt/s - k\varphi) \right\} \quad (2)$$

where a_k are modulation coefficients given by:

$$a_k = \text{MTF} \left(\frac{k \lambda_{\text{eff}}}{sD} \right) \cdot \frac{2 \sin(k\pi\delta)}{k\pi\delta} \cdot \frac{\sin(k\pi v \Delta t/s)}{k\pi v \Delta t/s} \quad (3)$$

I_0 is the average count rate from the star, given approximately

$$I_0 = 290\,000 \text{ Hz/cm}^2 \cdot A \cdot \delta \cdot 10^{-0.4B} \quad (4)$$

or, with the values of A and δ in section 1,

$$I_0 = 1.16 \cdot 10^{7-0.4B} \quad (5)$$

φ is the phase of the star with respect to the grid; this is the parameter to be determined. A phase error $\Delta\varphi$ corresponds to a position error with respect to the slits equal to $\Delta\eta = \frac{s}{2\pi} \Delta\varphi$.

We observe that the effect of the background current b is to decrease the effective modulation. In fact we can write (2) in the form

$$I(t) = (I_0 + b) \left\{ 1 + \sum_{k=1}^n a'_k \cos(k 2\pi vt/s - k\varphi) \right\} \quad (6)$$

where the modified modulation coefficients are:

$$a_k' = \frac{a_k}{1 + b/I_0} \quad (7)$$

and $(I_0 + b)$ is the resulting average count rate.

3. Precision of phase determination by Fourier analysis.

The actual phase φ in (6) may be estimated from the counts c_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, of the m samples corresponding to the N slits,

$$m = \frac{Ns}{v \Delta t} \quad (8)$$

This may be accomplished by Fourier analysis of $\{c_i\}$. Let φ_0 be the a priori phase and $\hat{\varphi}$ the estimated phase. We have then:

$$\hat{\varphi} = \varphi_0 + \arctan \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m c_i \sin[2\pi v t_i / s - \varphi_0]}{\sum_{i=1}^m c_i \cos[2\pi v t_i / s - \varphi_0]} \quad (9)$$

where $t_i = t_0 + i \Delta t$ is the time of the i -th sample. Since $\hat{\varphi}$ is (in principle) independent of φ_0 , we may take $\varphi_0 = \varphi$, the actual phase; the error of the phase determination is then

$$\Delta\varphi \equiv \hat{\varphi} - \varphi \approx \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m c_i \sin[2\pi v i \Delta t / s - \varphi]}{\sum_{i=1}^m c_i \cos[2\pi v i \Delta t / s - \varphi]} \quad (10)$$

(putting, arbitrarily, $t_0 = 0$), since $\Delta\varphi$ is expected to be $\ll 1$ so that we can use the approximation $\arctan x \approx x$.

Taking the expectation of the numerator of (10) we get:

$$E\left[\sum_{i=1}^m c_i \sin[2\pi v i \Delta t / s - \varphi]\right] = \sum_{i=1}^m E(c_i) \sin[2\pi v i \Delta t / s - \varphi]. \quad (11)$$

But the expected number of counts in sample i , $E(c_i)$, is the count rate at time $t_i = i \Delta t$ times the sample period Δt , i.e.

$(I_0 + b)$

$$E(c_i) = \Delta t (I_0 + b) \left\{ 1 + \sum_k a_k' \cos(k 2\pi v i \Delta t / s - k\varphi) \right\}. \quad (12)$$

Since we sample an integer number of fundamental periods, we find, inserting (12) into (11), that all terms cancel out, thanks to the orthogonality of the Fourier components. Thus, the expectation of the numerator in (10) is zero, i.e. $E(\Delta\varphi) = 0$, as required for an unbiased estimator.

For the denominator of (10), however, we find:

$$\begin{aligned} E\left[\sum_{i=1}^m c_i \cos[2\pi v i \Delta t / s - \varphi]\right] &= \sum_{i=1}^m \Delta t (I_0 + b) a_1' \cos^2[2\pi v i \Delta t / s - \varphi] \\ &= \frac{m}{2} \Delta t (I_0 + b) a_1' \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Since $a_1' \neq 0$, (14) will always be the dominating term in the denominator and we may write (10) as

$$\Delta\varphi = \frac{2}{m \Delta t (I_0 + b) a_1'} \sum_{i=1}^m c_i \sin[2\pi v i \Delta t / s - \varphi]. \quad (14)$$

Since $E(\Delta\varphi) = 0$, we may subtract this from (15) to get:

$$\Delta\varphi = \frac{2}{m \Delta t (I_0 + b) a_1'} \sum_{i=1}^m [c_i - E(c_i)] \sin[2\pi v i \Delta t / s - \varphi] \quad (15)$$

The variance of the estimated phase $\hat{\varphi}$ is $\sigma_{\hat{\varphi}}^2 \equiv E[\Delta\varphi^2]$.

Squaring (16) we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\varphi^2 &= \left(\frac{2}{m \Delta t (I_0 + b) a_1'} \right)^2 \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m [c_i - E(c_i)][c_j - E(c_j)] \\ &\quad \cdot \sin[2\pi v i \Delta t / s - \varphi] \sin[2\pi v j \Delta t / s - \varphi], \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

In taking the expectation of (17) we note that, from the well-known properties of photon statistics,

$$E \left\{ [c_i - E(c_i)][c_j - E(c_j)] \right\} = \begin{cases} E(c_i) & \text{if } i=j \\ 0 & \text{if } i \neq j. \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Hence

$$E(\Delta\varphi^2) = \left(\frac{2}{m\Delta t(I_0+b)a_1'} \right)^2 \sum_{i=1}^m E(c_i) \sin^2 [2\pi v_i \Delta t/s - \varphi]. \quad (19)$$

Using the identity $\sin^2 x = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \cos(2x)$ and inserting (12), we find that only the Fourier terms of order 0 and 2 contribute to the sum in (19), which becomes:

$$\sigma_\varphi^2 = \left(\frac{2}{m\Delta t(I_0+b)a_1'} \right)^2 \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{1}{2} \Delta t(I_0+b) [1 - a_2' \cos^2(4\pi v_i \Delta t/s - \varphi)] \quad (20)$$

or

$$\sigma_\varphi^2 = \frac{2 - a_2'}{m\Delta t(I_0+b)a_1'^2} \quad (21)$$

Note that $m\Delta t = T$ is the time needed for the star to cross the N slits, and $m\Delta t(I_0+b)$ is the total number of counts during this time. The positional mean error along the scan is

$$\sigma_\eta = \frac{s}{2\pi} \sigma_\varphi, \text{ i.e.}$$

$$\sigma_\eta = \frac{s}{2\pi} \frac{1}{a_1'} \left[\frac{2 - a_2'}{T(I_0+b)} \right]^{1/2} \quad (22)$$

Note that a_1' and a_2' depend on b/I_0 according to (7).

4. Evaluation of modulation coefficients a_k

We need to evaluate at least a_1 and a_2 for both vertical slits and inclined (45°) slits. In (3), the only remaining uncertain factor is the MTF. For a rectangular pupil with obscuration ratio $\eta = 0.5$

we find the MTF for the two slit systems as in Fig. 1. (6)

In evaluating (3) it should be remembered, that the effective grid period for the inclined slits is $3'' \cos 45^\circ \approx 2.12''$, which must be used in the expression for the argument of the MTF. However, the $\delta = 0.2$ is the same for the two slit systems, and so is the ratio v/s (since the spin rate component at 45° is $150''/\text{sec} \cdot \cos 45^\circ$) hence the last two factors in (3) are the same for the two slit systems. - We find the coefficients:

k	$a_k(0^\circ)$	$a_k(45^\circ)$
0	1.00	1.00
1	1.40	0.95
2	0.75	0.25
3	0.41	0.08
4	0.15	0.00
5	0.00	-
6	-0.09	-
7	-0.07	-
8	0.00	-

The intensity modulation curves in Fig. 2 were constructed from these coefficients.

5. Evaluation of background current

The background current b is made up of two components: dark current due to (mainly) thermal emission of electrons from photocathode (this is strongly dependent of temperature), and the sky background, which depends on the total area of the

slits, the sky direction and the position of the Earth relative to the two FOV's. (7)

5.1. Dark current

According to Aeritalia (I-117) the typical S20 thermal background noise corresponds to $6000 \text{ photons/sec.cm}^2$ at 20°C . With quantum efficiency 0.2 and the same photocathode area as for the IDT (i.e. 15 mm diameter), this would give a dark current of 2000 Hz at 20°C .

This seems to be a bit high, but can be reduced e.g. by:

- using a less noisy cathode material (e.g. bi-alkali, which has 5-50 times smaller dark current than S20, while giving almost the same sensitivity);
- using a smaller cathode area (depends on available tubes and necessary modification of star mapper optical relay);
- cooling. (expensive and probably incompatible with thermal requirements for optical system).

It seems almost certain that a combination of the first two methods easily can bring down the dark current below 200 Hz.

However, in the calculations to follow, we shall use both the pessimistic value 2000 Hz and, for comparison, the more optimistic 200 Hz.

5.2. Sky background

The sky brightness may be expressed in the equivalent number of 10th magnitude stars per square degree. Using photographic (blue) magnitudes, we find (Allen: Astrophysical Quantities, 1973, p. 134):

$B=10$
Source B stars per square degree

Zodiacal light (away from zodiac):	60
Faint stars, $B > 6$, depending on galactic latitude:	16 - 140 (mean value = 50)
Diffuse galactic light	10

Typical total brightness: 120 $B=10$ stars/square degree.

Most of the time, scattered light from the Earth will be negligible.

To account for the two superposed FOV's, we double this figure and find an equivalent of one $B=4.0$ star per square degree.

Eq. (4) then gives (with $A=200 \text{ cm}^2$ and $\delta=1$) $1.46 \cdot 10^6 \text{ Hz per square degree}$. 16 slits of width 0.6 and length $20'$ gives an area $8.89 \cdot 10^{-4}$ square degree $\Rightarrow$ 1300 Hz for sky background.

Combining the dark current and average sky background we find the total background current

$$b = 3300 \text{ Hz} \quad (1500 \text{ Hz with improved detector})$$

6. Evaluation of star mapper accuracy as function of star magnitude

For $N=8$ slits we get $T = Ns/v = 0.16 \text{ sec}$. With numerical values inserted for T , I_0 , b and s , we obtain the formula:

$$\sigma_{\eta} = 3.50 \cdot 10^{0.2B-4} \cdot \frac{1}{a_1} \sqrt{2f(B) - a_2} \quad \text{arcsec} \quad (24)$$

where

$$f(B) = 1 + \frac{b}{I_0} = 1 + \frac{3300}{1.16 \cdot 10^{7-0.4B}} \quad (25)$$

Results for the two grid systems are given in the table below, (9)
with background current $b = 3300$ and $b = 1500$ Hz (latter in parentheses).

Table 1: Mean errors of position along scan relative to vertical (0°) and inclined (45°) slits. Background $b = 3300$ Hz (1500 Hz).

Blue magnitude B	$\sigma_\eta (0^\circ)$	$\sigma_\eta (45^\circ)$	σ_ξ	M
3	0.0011	0.0019	0.0022	0.6
4	0.0018	0.0031	0.0036	1.9
5	0.0029	0.0050	0.0058	5.6
6	0.0047 (0.0045)	0.0080	0.0093	17
7	0.0080 (0.0075)	0.013	0.015	49
8	0.0156 (0.013)	0.024 (0.022)	0.028 (0.026)	130
9	0.030 (0.024)	0.047 (0.039)	0.056 (0.046)	370
10	0.066 (0.049)	0.10 (0.077)	0.12 (0.091)	1000
11	0.16 (0.11)	0.23 (0.17)	0.28 (0.20)	2700
12	0.38 (0.26)	0.57 (0.39)	0.69 (0.47)	6900

The table also gives $\sigma_\xi = \sqrt{\sigma_\eta^2(0^\circ) + \sigma_\eta^2(45^\circ)}$, i.e. the resulting mean error for the coordinate perpendicular to the scan (Acritalia, II-262, assuming $\sigma_w = 0$), and finally $M =$ expected number of stars of magnitude $B \pm 0.5$ encountered by star mapper per scan (2.4 hours). This M is obtained as twice the product of the area on sky swept by star mapper ($20' \times 360^\circ$) and the star density according to Allen (p. 243).

Note that at any particular time, the slits occupy an area $16 \times 0.6 \times 20' = 7.4 \times 10^{-6} \times (20' \times 360^\circ)$, so that the probability of getting a parasitic star of magnitude B in the slits is approx. $10^{-5} M$ i.e. $< 1\%$ for $B < 10$.

Figure 2: Intensity modulation behind vertical (0°) and inclined (45°) slits. (No background; normalized to average count rate.)

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